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Optimizing Plastic Waste Utilization in Bottle Manufacturing: A Comparative Analysis of HDPE, PP, and PET

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Abstract

Plastic has emerged as a technology of paramount importance due to its versatile properties, often replacing metals in various applications. Consequently, it is logical for individuals to seek practical solutions by transitioning from traditional metal, glass, and wood processing technologies to those involving plastic. This study employs quantitative methods for its research approach. Following the collection of data, conclusions regarding further testing steps can be drawn. The objective of this testing is to determine the most suitable type of plastic waste for bottle production. The findings reveal that, in the manufacturing of bottles, HDPE plastic waste utilization is only 1.96%, whereas PP plastic waste uses 2.34%, and PET plastic waste employs 1.53%. As this research concludes, several key findings are noted: The optimal selection of plastic waste for producing 30ml bottles is HDPE; temperature significantly affects bottle manufacturing, with 190°C identified as the most optimal temperature for HDPE processing. In these tests, the resultant product closely resembled the intended mold design, requiring only 1.96% of HDPE waste material.

Keywords: *Plastic Waste Utilization; Bottle Manufacturing; HDPE, PP, PET Comparison; Quantitative Research Method; Temperature Influence in Production.*

Introduction

Plastic, as one of the most influential technological innovations, has assumed a critical role in various aspects of life. Its characteristics – lightweight, resistance to moisture and corrosion, ease of molding, and efficient production processes – make it a frequent substitute for metals. This phenomenon is evident from the public's preference for practical solutions, namely shifting from metal, glass, and wood processing technologies to plastic-based technologies[1].

In Indonesia, particularly, the development of plastic products demonstrates significant progress. From a qualitative perspective, both the quality and the variety of plastic products have been continuously improving[2]. The plastic industry has produced a diverse range of products including household appliances, electronic tools, automotive components, and many more. This advancement reflects not only innovation in design and functionality but also an adaptation to the evolving market needs and environmental sustainability demands[3].

Amidst global concerns about the environmental impact of plastic use, innovations in recycling and the development of biodegradable plastics have become crucial topics in research and industry development[4]. This reflects efforts to create a balance between

economic benefits and environmental responsibility, enabling plastic to continue evolving as a material that is not only practical and versatile but also environmentally friendly[5].

The blow molding machine is a sophisticated device specifically designed for the bottle manufacturing process, based on the fundamental principle of blowing bottle preforms. This process initiates by heating the bottle preforms to a soft and elastic state. Subsequently, these preforms are inserted into a mold, known as the mold cavity[6], [7]. At this stage, a specific air pressure is applied to inject the softened preforms, causing them to expand and conform to the mold's shape. Consequently, the preforms transform into a bottle product or profile, matching the predetermined design of the mold[8], [9].

A key component in the blow molding machine is the 'injection blowing tools.' This tool encompasses a vital part named 'injection tools,' which acts as a mechanism for injecting or blowing high-pressure air into the bottle preform[10], [11]. This high-pressure air, sourced from a compressor, functions to stretch the preform to fill the mold cavity, thus achieving the final bottle shape with high precision[12], [13].

The blow molding process is not only efficient in creating bottles of various shapes and sizes but also allows for the use of diverse types of plastics. The result is the production of uniform, strong bottles that can be tailored to specific needs, both in industrial scales and daily use. With this technology, the bottle manufacturing industry is capable of producing high-quality products with optimal time and cost efficiency[14]–[16].

In the bottle manufacturing process using blow moulding machines, injection tools play a critical role. The materials used in these tools must meet specific criteria, being lightweight and highly resistant to the temperature intensity generated by the bottle preforms, which can reach around $\pm 100^{\circ}\text{C}$ [17]. Furthermore, the injection blowing tools integrated with the blow moulding machine need to be designed with high strength. This is essential to ensure that these tools can withstand the load from the injection tools and the mold cavity during the bottle-making process[18], [19].

In the context of producing 30 ml bottles, the selection of high-quality plastic types becomes crucial. Several plastics suitable and commonly used in bottle manufacturing are Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET), High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE), and Polypropylene (PP). Each of these plastics has unique characteristics that suit specific needs in bottle production. PET is known for its clarity and strength, HDPE offers density and resistance to chemicals, while PP is renowned for its flexibility and heat resistance.

The objectives of this research are to determine the most suitable type of plastic waste to produce plastic bottles, considering strength and durability. To analyze the efficiency of using HDPE, PP, and PET waste in the bottle manufacturing process and evaluate the characteristics of each material. To identify challenges and weaknesses in the process of making bottles using these plastic wastes, including the impact of process temperature on the final product quality.

Methodology

The research location chosen for this study is CV. Star Umroh Engineering, situated on Jalan Menteng VII, Gang Wakaf Ujung, in the Kecamatan Medan Denai area of Medan, North Sumatra. This facility was selected due to its suitable equipment and infrastructure for conducting research related to plastic waste processing. The equipment utilized in this study includes a Shredding Machine, which serves to break down plastic waste into smaller particles, facilitating easier processing. Additionally, an Injection Molding Machine is employed to reshape the shredded plastic waste into new products. Another essential tool used is a Scale, crucial for measuring and ensuring the accuracy of the plastic waste weight

used in the research. The primary materials for this study are plastic wastes, comprising three main types: High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE), Polypropylene (PP), and Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET). These types of plastics were chosen due to their distinct characteristics, providing a comprehensive perspective on the potential of plastic waste processing in various applications.

In this research, data collection was conducted with the objective of analyzing and calculating the performance of three different types of plastic waste. Each type of plastic waste used in the study was subjected to three trials. The purpose of these repeated experiments is to gather reliable data and enable a more accurate comparison between the various types of plastic waste. Temperature, a key parameter in this process, was varied at three distinct points: 170°C, 180°C, and 190°C. This variation is crucial to understanding how temperature changes affect the quality and efficiency of the bottle manufacturing process. The final stage of this research focuses on determining the best material for the production of 30 ml bottles. This involves an in-depth analysis of the properties of the materials produced at different temperatures and processing conditions to identify the most effective and efficient for bottle production. The ultimate outcome of this research is expected to provide significant insights into the utilization of plastic waste in the bottle manufacturing industry, as well as its contribution to environmentally friendly and sustainable practices.

The research process commences with the thorough preparation of all necessary tools and materials. Upon completion of the preparations, the next step is to conduct a Blowing Test on the injection molding machine. This test aims to ensure that the machine is capable of producing plastic bottles utilizing waste HDPE, PP, and PET as raw materials. Following the Blowing Test, the results are then subjected to a visual inspection. This visual examination is crucial to confirm that there are no apparent defects on the produced plastic bottles, such as deformation, cracking, or other quality issues that may have arisen during the blowing process. If the visual inspection results meet the established standards, the research proceeds to the analysis phase. This analysis involves more detailed testing of the plastic bottles, covering aspects such as strength, rigidity, and other potentially relevant characteristics pertaining to the quality and utility of the bottles. The outcomes of this analysis are determinant in deciding whether the production process can continue or if adjustments are needed in the machinery or process parameters. Upon the completion of the analysis, all relevant findings and data are compiled and summarized in a research report. This report encompasses all aspects of the research procedure, including methodology, test results, data analysis, and recommendations for further development. This report is instrumental in understanding the efficacy of the bottle production process from plastic waste and provides insights for future improvements. Finally, once the report is finalized, the research is considered to be concluded. Figure 1 shows the injection molding machine used in this research.

Figure 1: Injection molding machine

Result and Discussion

This research aimed to determine the most suitable type of plastic waste for bottle production. Through the analysis of the provided graph, it was found that each type of plastic exhibits different strengths and durability, offering crucial insights for material selection. According to the data processed and presented in Figure 2, it is observed that in the bottle manufacturing process, HDPE plastic waste requires about 1.96% of the total plastic waste, whereas PP plastic waste requires 2.34%, and PET plastic waste needs 1.53%. A significant finding from this research is that PP plastic demonstrates a superior weight advantage compared to HDPE and PET. This indicates the potential of PP as a more efficient material for bottle manufacturing in terms of material consumption. Additionally, the study reveals that although HDPE and PET require a lower proportion in bottle production, they possess specific characteristics that might make them more suitable for certain applications based on strength and durability requirements. This research provides valuable insights into the distinct characteristics of different types of plastic waste and their implications in bottle manufacturing. These findings are immensely useful for the plastic processing industry in optimizing material selection based on specific criteria, such as strength, weight, and material efficiency, thus facilitating more sustainable and efficient bottle production.

A significant difference in weight between PP, HDPE, and PET plastics was observed in this research. PP plastic, being heavier than HDPE and PET, exhibited limitations in the testing phase. Specifically, bottles made from PP plastic waste often did not fully fill at the tip. This issue arises due to the highly brittle nature of PP plastic, which is prone to cracking, necessitating the use of more raw material in the bottle manufacturing process to achieve the desired shape. Conversely, HDPE plastic, with its lighter weight, results in bottles that require less weight and raw material. The advantage of HDPE lies in its ability to fill molds more efficiently, producing bottles that are fully formed and closely resemble the mold's shape. These testing results suggest that HDPE may be more suitable for certain applications where material usage efficiency and success in fully achieving mold shapes are primary considerations. This finding provides crucial insights for the plastic processing industry in determining the appropriate choice of raw materials according to the specific needs of the product.

Figure 2: Product Defect Testing Results

In the initial test conducted at temperatures ranging from 170°C to 180°C using HDPE plastic waste, the resulting bottles were not yet perfected. Although these bottles resembled the intended mold shape, their structure appeared extremely thin and prone to cracking. This issue arose due to the incomplete melting of the shredded plastic waste, leaving clusters of un-melted plastic that were not uniformly mixed. Figure 3 depicts the outcome of bottles produced within this temperature range, highlighting deficiencies in the bottle forming process that need to be addressed to achieve a higher quality product that meets the expected standards.

Figure 3: Test results on HDPE plastic

Figure 4 presents the results from the second test, conducted at temperatures ranging from 180°C to 190°C using HDPE plastic waste. In this trial, the bottles reached their final form, but several issues were observed. The bottles underwent shrinkage, and their structure remained thin and prone to cracking. A primary cause of these issues is the excessively rapid cooling process following the bottle formation, which does not allow adequate time for the plastic to optimally rearrange its structure. The figure provides a clear visualization of the bottles produced within the 180°C to 190°C temperature range, highlighting areas that require improvements in the manufacturing process to produce a higher quality product.

Figure 4: Second test results on HDPE plastic.

Figure 5 displays the results from the third test conducted at temperatures ranging from 190°C to 200°C using HDPE plastic waste. In this trial, the bottles were successfully formed, but they exhibited defects characterized by lines on the outer surface of the product. This issue was attributed to the use of molds or casts that had uneven surfaces, impacting the final quality of the product. Such defects are critical as they can affect both the strength and aesthetic appeal of the product. The figure provides a visual representation of the bottles produced within the 190°C to 200°C temperature range, highlighting the importance of mold quality in the bottle manufacturing process to ensure the production of products that are not only functional but also meet aesthetic standards.

Figure 5: Third test results on HDPE plastic.

In the first series of tests conducted at temperatures between 190°C and 200°C using Polypropylene (PP) plastic waste, it was observed that the bottles produced did not fully fill the molds. Additionally, these bottles were characterized by their thin structure and susceptibility to cracking. This issue arose because the plastic waste inserted into the injection molding machine did not melt completely, resulting in incomplete filling of the mold. This phenomenon indicates the limitations of PP material at these temperatures in the bottle manufacturing process. Figure 6 presents a visual representation of the bottles produced within the 190°C to 200°C temperature range, clearly illustrating the challenges

faced in manufacturing bottles using PP plastic waste at high temperatures and the implications of plastic melting quality on the final product outcome.

Figure 6: First test results on PP plastic

Figure 7 illustrates the results from the second test conducted at temperatures ranging from 200°C to 210°C using Polypropylene (PP) plastic waste. In this experiment, it was observed that the upper part of the bottle was not fully filled, and it exhibited cracking. This issue arose due to the inherent brittleness of PP plastic waste at temperatures between 200°C and 210°C. The figure provides a visual representation of the bottles produced within this temperature range. It highlights the challenges associated with using PP plastic waste at high temperatures in the bottle manufacturing process and underscores the unsuitability of PP plastic for such temperature ranges.

Figure 7: Second test results on PP plastic

In the third test conducted at temperatures ranging from 210°C to 220°C using Polypropylene (PP) plastic waste, the resulting bottles had reached their final form. However, the upper portion of the bottles exhibited brittleness and thinning. This issue was attributed to the rapid hardening of the plastic waste at these temperatures. The figure depicting the results of bottles produced at temperatures between 210°C and 220°C can be observed in

Figure 8. This visual representation provides insight into the challenges associated with using PP plastic waste at high temperatures in the bottle manufacturing process, which significantly impacts the final product quality.

Figure 8: Third test results on PP plastic

In the first test conducted at temperatures ranging from 160°C to 180°C using Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) plastic waste, the results indicated that the produced products did not achieve the ideal capacity or conform to the desired mold. This issue arose because the shredded plastic waste hardened before entering the mold or did not melt perfectly. The figure depicting the results of bottles produced at temperatures between 160°C and 180°C can be observed in Figure 9. This visual representation provides insight into the challenges associated with using PET plastic waste at high temperatures in the bottle manufacturing process, which significantly impacts the final product quality.

Figure 9: First test results on PET plastic

In the second test conducted at temperatures ranging from 180°C to 190°C using Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) plastic waste, the results were similar to the first test. The bottle mold was not fully filled, and shrinkage occurred. This was due to the temperature being insufficient to ensure optimal molding. The figure depicting the results of bottles produced at temperatures between 180°C and 190°C can be observed in Figure 10. This

visualization illustrates the challenges associated with using PET plastic waste at certain temperatures in the bottle manufacturing process, which affects the final product's quality.

Figure 10: Second test results on PET plastic

In the third test conducted at temperatures ranging from 190°C to 200°C using Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) plastic waste, the resulting bottles had reached their final form but exhibited a darkened coloration. This discoloration occurred due to the excessively high temperature applied during the process. The figure depicting the results of bottles produced at temperatures between 190°C and 200°C can be observed in Figure 11. This visualization provides insight into the impact of high temperatures on PET plastic waste in the bottle manufacturing process, resulting in discoloration that may affect the final product's quality.

The study reveals that PP waste exhibits superior weight advantages compared to HDPE and PET, indicating the potential of PP as a more efficient material. However, PP is more prone to cracking and often fails to completely fill the mold. HDPE waste, being lighter, produces more material-efficient bottles and achieves a shape closer to the intended mold. It was also found that at certain temperatures, HDPE and PET exhibited issues such as thinning structures and a tendency to crack, as well as color changes in PET at high temperatures.

Conclusion

The conclusion drawn from this research is that the efficacy of each type of plastic waste in bottle manufacturing is determined by its distinct properties. Polypropylene (PP) presents notable weight benefits, contributing to lighter bottles, which is a desirable attribute in certain applications. However, PP's limitations become apparent in its mold-filling capability and a higher propensity for cracking, posing challenges in achieving consistent product quality. High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE), on the other hand, excels in mold-filling efficiency, enabling the creation of bottles that closely align with design specifications. Despite this advantage, HDPE encounters significant performance issues at specific processing temperatures, which can impact the structural integrity and aesthetic qualities of the bottles. Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) is noteworthy for its tendency to undergo color changes when exposed to high temperatures during the molding process, a factor that could affect the visual appeal and perceived quality of the final product. This research is instrumental for the plastic processing industry, as it underscores the necessity of a nuanced approach to material selection. Manufacturers must consider a balance of

strength, weight, and material efficiency when choosing the appropriate type of recycled plastic. Additionally, the findings emphasize the critical role of temperature control in the manufacturing process. Proper temperature management is essential not only for ensuring the physical and aesthetic qualities of the bottles but also for maximizing the potential of recycled materials. This study, therefore, not only aids in improving manufacturing practices but also contributes to the broader goal of sustainable and efficient use of plastic waste.

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Dadan Ramdan, (1) 1 (2024), Optimizing Plastic Waste Utilization in Bottle...

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